

Effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project on improving the character of students of SMAK 7 Penabur Jakarta

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History: Received: June 22, 2024 Revised: September 15, 2024 Accepted: September 18, 2024 Published: December 13, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Pancasila Student Profile, Independent Curriculum, Student Character</p> <p>*Corresponding Author: verry.jekson @bpkpenaburjakarta.or.id</p> <p>DOI:</p>	<p>This study examines the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) in improving the character of students at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta. The Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project is designed to integrate Pancasila values—such as belief in God, humanity, unity, democracy, and social justice—into daily student activities. The study aims to measure how effective the project is in shaping student character, identify factors influencing its effectiveness, and analyze student and teacher perceptions of the program. Using a quantitative research method with purposive sampling, data were collected through surveys and interviews. Results show that Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project positively impacts students' character development, particularly in areas of cooperation, critical thinking, and social responsibility. However, the study also highlights challenges, including varying levels of student engagement and resource limitations. The findings suggest that continuous evaluation and improvement of the program are necessary to maximize its benefits. The study implies that schools should provide better support for teachers and include more practical applications of Pancasila values in both curricular and extracurricular activities. It is recommended that future research explore long-term impacts and scalability of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project program across different educational settings. Overall, this study contributes to the theoretical understanding of character education and offers practical insights for improving value-based educational initiatives.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Education in Indonesia faces complex challenges during the era of globalization and rapid social change. Education must not only improve students' academic knowledge, but must also be able to build students' character so that they are ready to face an increasingly changing world. As the ideological basis of the Indonesian state, Pancasila offers important values such as divinity, humanity, unity, democracy and social justice. These values contribute to the formation of an honest and responsible young generation (Syafira et al., 2024).

One concrete effort to address this issue is to implement the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta. It is intended that Pancasila values be incorporated into students' daily activities, both inside and outside the classroom. The P5 program teaches students to believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, understand and appreciate diversity, cooperate and work together, be independent, think critically, and be

creative. The hope is that students are not only academically intelligent but also have strong characters that are in accordance with the values of Pancasila (Tambunan & Febrianti, 2023).

However, further research needs to be conducted, especially quantitatively, to determine whether the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) is successful in improving student character. Current research has not provided a comprehensive picture of the influence of P5 on student character building. As a result, this research is very important to find out how effective the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) is in building student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta. The school can make necessary evaluations and improvements to ensure that the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) program can really help students become people of character and ready to face future challenges if they know how the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) functions.

Based on the above, the research focus is as follows :

1. How effective is the Strengthening the Profile of Pancasila Students project in improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta?
2. What are the factors that influence the successful implementation of the Strengthening the Profile of Pancasila Students project at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta?
3. What do teachers and students think about the implementation of the Strengthening the Profile of Pancasila Students project at SMAK 7 PENABUR in Jakarta?

Research Objectives

This research aims to :

- a. Measuring the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project in improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.
- b. Identifying factors that influence the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.
- c. Analyzing student and teacher perceptions of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture conceptualized the "Pancasila Learner Profile" to describe the ideal traits that every Indonesian student is expected to possess. In this profile, there are six main dimensions: faith, piety, and noble character in God Almighty; global diversity; mutual cooperation; independence; critical thinking; and creativity. Each of these dimensions encompasses a range of values and competencies that are intended to shape students from a moral and social as well as academic perspective (Kemendikbud, 2024). For example, the aspect of faith and fear of God Almighty and noble character includes the formation of firm moral and spiritual attitudes and behaviors that reflect high ethics and integrity in daily life.

On the other hand, the global diversity dimension emphasizes how important it is to be able to appreciate and interact with different cultures. In an increasingly connected world, students are expected to understand and appreciate cultural differences and be able to communicate well with people from different cultures. In addition, this dimension encourages students to have a broad and inclusive perspective and the ability to adapt quickly to a diverse world environment. Competencies such as these are critical to shaping the next generation that will contribute constructively in the global arena.

Other dimensions, such as self-reliance, critical thinking, creativity, and mutual cooperation, emphasize cooperation and solidarity in achieving a common goal, while self-reliance teaches students to be able to rely on themselves and take responsibility for their choices. respectively. Critical reasoning emphasizes the ability to make informed decisions based on evidence and to

analyze and evaluate information objectively. In contrast, creative teaches students to think out-of-the-box, generate creative ideas, and find new ways to solve problems. The Pancasila Learner Profile aims to produce students who are not only academically intelligent, but also have strong character and are able to contribute positively to society by incorporating these six dimensions (Sartini et al., 2024).

Student Character Concept

In the context of education, student character encompasses a wide range of traits, values, and behaviors that reflect a person's personality. Some aspects of morals and ethics include honesty, responsibility, empathy, fairness, and the ability to cooperate and respect others. Character is formed through a long and consistent learning process rather than instantly. Character education focuses on embedding these positive principles in students' daily lives so that they can grow into honest and highly moral people (Kamiela, 2023).

The purpose of student character development is to produce students who not only perform well in school but also have strong personalities and can make useful contributions to society. Students who have good character are expected to face life's challenges in a positive and constructive way because they are able to show honesty in their every action, take responsibility for their decisions and behavior, have high empathy for others, and behave fairly towards others (Habibi, 2023).

Character education emphasizes how important it is to combine moral development and academic education. A well-rounded educational process does not only focus on the dissemination of knowledge; it also includes the formation of moral attitudes and principles. This can be achieved in various ways, such as project-based education, group discussions, extracurricular activities, and community service programs. Therefore, character education occurs not only in the classroom, but also in various activities that involve social interactions and life experiences (Arifin, 2017). This approach helps students internalize ethical and moral principles in their daily lives so that they are prepared to become responsive and positively contributing members of society.

Implementation of the the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project in schools

The the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) in schools involves various means and activities that aim to incorporate Pancasila values into students' daily lives. At SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta, the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) is implemented through group discussions, collaborative projects, extracurricular activities, spiritual activities, and community service programs. Students can talk about Pancasila values in group discussions, and collaborative projects encourage students to work together and solve problems collectively. In addition, extracurricular activities such as sports and cultural clubs aim to instill a sense of community and responsibility. Conversely, community service programs give students the opportunity to directly participate in activities that benefit their environment so that they can apply the values of humanity and gotong royong.

The aim of this approach is to incorporate the values of Pancasila into the school culture. Providing examples of behavior in accordance with these values is a very important task for teachers and school employees. They not only give theoretical lessons, but also demonstrate the values of Pancasila in real life with their students. In addition, the school conducts periodic evaluations to find out how effective the implementation of Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) is. These evaluations involve direct observation, surveys and feedback from students, teachers and parents. The results are used to improve the program and ensure that it remains relevant and effective in building students' character in accordance with

Pancasila values. This comprehensive and sustainable method is expected to produce a learning environment that supports students' overall character development (Mustoip, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Character education theory and the constructivist approach to learning are the two main approaches on which this research is based. According to character education theory, building moral and ethical values is an important part of holistic education. Character education aims to build positive traits such as honesty, responsibility, empathy, and cooperation, which are expected to produce moral and noble people (Agus et al., 2022). This theory also emphasizes that character must be formed through a consistent and sustainable process in various aspects of student life, both inside and outside school. In other words, character education is not only limited to formal teaching; it also involves real-world examples and experiences that students can internalize.

The constructivist approach, driven by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, adds an important element to this concept. According to constructivism, effective learning occurs when students actively participate in the learning process and improve their own knowledge through interaction with others and their environment (Sinaga et al., 2024). Vygotsky emphasized the importance of social and cultural interaction in the learning process, while Piaget concentrated on individual cognitive development. This constructivist approach is particularly relevant for the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) as the program aims to provide students with opportunities to experience and internalize Pancasila values in real life. Students not only gain a theoretical understanding of these values, but they can also apply them in their daily lives. They participate in collaborative projects, conduct group discussions, and follow community service programs. Therefore, P5 provides students with opportunities for active and contextualized learning. This allows them to gain a deep understanding of the principles of Pancasila and how they can apply them in their daily lives.

Research Hypothesis

Based on the literature review and theoretical framework that has been discussed, the hypothesis of this study is :

1. The implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) is effective in improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.
2. There is a significant relationship between students' involvement in P5 and the improvement of their character, especially in the dimensions of faith and devotion to God Almighty, noble character, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical reasoning, and creativity.
3. Factors such as teacher support, active student participation, and a supportive school environment have a positive influence on P5 effectiveness.

With this hypothesis, the research will explore and test the assumptions regarding the impact of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) on student character development. This research is expected to provide a deeper insight into the implementation and effectiveness of this program at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta

METHOD

Research methods are an important part of a study because they determine how the research will be conducted and how data will be collected, analyzed, and interpreted (Ismayani, 2019). This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach to measure the effectiveness of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) on improving student character at SMAK 7

PENABUR Jakarta. This helps provide an overview of the sample characteristics and initial measurement results (Asari et al., 2023).

This study involved grade X students of SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta who have adopted the independent curriculum. The purposive sampling method was used for sampling. Students involved in the P5 program were selected as the experimental group, and students who were not involved in the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) were selected as the control group. The number of samples used in this study was governed by the number of representativeness and the minimum number required for valid statistical analysis (Istiqomah et al., 2023).

Data Collection Technique

This research uses several data collection techniques to obtain relevant and comprehensive data. The questionnaire was used to measure students' perceptions and attitudes towards Pancasila values and changes in their character; it consisted of several closed and open-ended questions intended to gather information about students' experiences during the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5). The observation technique was used to track student activities directly. Documentation involves collecting data from various school documents, such as program reports, activity records, and evaluation documents. These documents can provide additional information on the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) and how it impacts students' character

Research Instruments

This study used three research instruments: questionnaires, observation sheets, and documentation formats. The questionnaire was created using a Likert scale to measure students' attitudes and perceptions with an answer range from strongly disagree to strongly agree, and the observation sheet was designed to systematically record students' behavior during P5 activities. To ensure that the instruments could produce accurate and consistent data, their validity and reliability were tested first.

The data analysis technique used normality and hypothesis tests using SPSS version 26. Respondents involved in this study were students of SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta with a sample size of 50 respondents, and came from class X who had implemented an independent curriculum. Data collection uses a closed questionnaire, where respondents only provide answers by checking the options that have been given. Research always has variables. Research variables are features, objects, or individuals that have been determined by researchers to be examined to determine the results. This research examines two variables, namely the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project variable (X) and the student character variable (Y). The following presents the direction of research on the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) on improving the character of SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta students :

X : Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5)

Y : Student Character

Figure 1. Research Design Scheme

In quantitative type research, it is known as validity test and reliability test. Validity is a term used to explain the accuracy of a measuring instrument, namely the accuracy of measurement of what should be measured (Benu & Benu, 2021). Validity is needed because it is a signpost for obtaining the right data from respondents (students). Meanwhile, the reliability test is carried out to find out how reliable an instrument is so that an instrument can be accounted for. According to Yusuf, reliability is the consistency or stability of an instrument's score on the same individual, and is given at different times (Yusuf, 2016). Related to this, to find the level of instrument reliability, researchers utilize SPSS version 26.

With this structured research method, the research is expected to provide valid and reliable information about the effectiveness of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project in improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Validity Test

The validity test was carried out to determine the extent to which the measuring instrument (instrument) used in this study was able to measure what should be measured. In this study, validity was tested using Pearson's correlation between each item and the overall total score.

Table 1. Validity Test of SPSS 26 Processing Results

Question	Pearson Correlation	Significance (Sig.)
P1	0.842	0.00
P2	0.803	0.00
P3	0,788	0.00
P4	0,862	0.00
P5	0,875	0.00
P6	0.846	0.00
P7	0.780	0.00
P8	0.779	0.00
P9	0.853	0.00
P10	0.877	0.00
P11	0.740	0.00
P12	0.892	0.00

Pearson Correlation Results (r table = 0.279)

If the value of r count $>$ r table, then the question variable is valid

If the value of r count $<$ r table, then the question variable is invalid

The validity test results using Pearson correlation indicate that all items in the research instrument have high validity. This is indicated by the Pearson correlation value, which is significant at the 99% confidence level.

High Correlation:

- All items have high correlation values with the total score, ranging from 0.740 to 0.892.
- This high correlation indicates that each item has a strong relationship with the construct measured by the instrument.

Statistical Significance:

- The significance value (Sig.) for all items is 0.000, which means the relationship is highly statistically significant.
- With a Sig. value much smaller than 0.05, it can be said that the correlation found does not occur by chance.

Instrument Validity:

- The high Pearson correlation value and very strong statistical significance indicate that the instrument is valid.
- This research instrument is able to measure the intended construct well and can be relied upon for further research.

2. Reliability Test

Reliability is the extent to which the measurement results can be trusted or consistent if repeated measurements are made under the same conditions. This study's reliability test used Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.958	12

Figure 2. Reliability Test of SPSS 26 Processing Results

If the Cronbach Alpha value > 0.6 , then the questionnaire instrument is reliable (reliable)

If the Cronbach Alpha value < 0.6 , then the questionnaire instrument is not reliable (not reliable)

Cronbach's Alpha value :

- The Cronbach's Alpha value obtained is 0.958.
- This value is very high, close to 1, which indicates an excellent level of internal consistency among the items in the instrument.

Number of Items :

- The tested instrument consisted of 12 items.
- The large number of items in this instrument contributes to the high Cronbach's Alpha value, as more items can increase overall reliability.

Conclusion:

High Reliability:

- With a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.958, the instruments used in this study are highly reliable.
- This shows that the items in the instrument are consistent in measuring the same concept and can be trusted to be used in repeated measurements.

Use of Instruments :

- This instrument can be used with high confidence that the measurement results will be consistent and reliable.
- The high level of reliability also indicates that this instrument has good quality and is suitable for measuring the effectiveness of the implementation of the project on strengthening the Pancasila student profile (P5) on improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.

These results provide confidence that the instruments used in the study have excellent reliability, so the data collected with these instruments can be considered consistent and reliable.

3. Pearson Correlation Analysis

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) :

- All Pearson correlation values are greater than 0.279 (table value), indicating a strong relationship between P5 effectiveness and student character improvement.
- The correlation values ranged from 0.740 to 0.892, indicating a very strong relationship between the variables.

- c. The direction of the relationship is positive, which means that an increase in the effectiveness of P5 is related to an increase in student character.

Statistical Significance (Sig.):

- a. All significance values were 0.00, meaning the relationship was highly statistically significant at the 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$).
- b. With such a small Sig. value, we can conclude that the relationship found is not coincidental and is highly significant.

Conclusion :

- a. Based on the results of Pearson correlation analysis, there is a very strong and significant relationship between the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) and the improvement of student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.
- b. The high correlation value indicates that the more effective the implementation of the project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students (P5), the higher the improvement of student character.
- c. These results provide strong evidence that the Pancasila (P5) student profile strengthening project program has a significant positive impact on student character, supporting the objectives of the program.

This analysis corroborates the importance of the implementation of the project on strengthening the Pancasila learner profile (P5) in improving student character, showing that the program has achieved its objectives very well.

Discussion

The results of this study show that the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta significantly improved student character. These findings are consistent with the research hypothesis, which stated that P5 is effective in shaping student character, particularly in the dimensions of faith and piety toward God, collaboration, global diversity, independence, critical thinking, and creativity. Moreover, the findings indicate that factors such as teacher support, active student participation, and a supportive school environment play a crucial role in the success of the P5 program.

These results align with character education theory, which emphasizes the importance of developing moral and ethical values as an integral part of education. According to Agus et al., (2022), character education focuses on cultivating positive traits such as honesty, responsibility, and empathy. This research supports that theory, as students involved in the P5 program showed significant improvements in these traits.

Furthermore, the findings reinforce the constructivist approach to learning, which emphasizes the importance of active student engagement in constructing their own knowledge and understanding through social interaction (Sinaga et al., 2024). P5 provides students with the opportunity to learn Pancasila values through hands-on experiences, such as collaborative projects, group discussions, and community service programs. This supports Vygotsky's view on the importance of the social environment in the learning process. By actively participating in activities based on Pancasila values, students not only understand these values theoretically but also internalize them in their daily lives.

This study also aligns with research conducted by Tambunan & Febrianti (2023), which found that integrating Pancasila values into students' daily activities through the P5 program in other schools in Indonesia also resulted in significant improvements in student character. Their study showed that students actively involved in the P5 program were better able to demonstrate

collaboration, independence, and critical thinking compared to students not engaged in the program.

On the other hand, this study offers new perspectives on the importance of teacher support and a supportive school environment as key factors in the effectiveness of P5. Teacher guidance in mentoring students and creating a conducive environment for character development has proven to be one of the determinants of the program's success. This finding is consistent with the research of Habibi (2023), which showed that teachers play a crucial role in instilling moral and ethical values in character education.

However, the study also revealed some challenges, such as differences in the level of student participation in the P5 program, which affected the program's effectiveness. Some students who were less active in P5 activities showed slower character development compared to those who fully engaged. This finding suggests that the success of P5 not only depends on the program's design but also on student motivation and active participation in these activities.

Overall, the findings of this study support the theory and previous research, demonstrating that integrating Pancasila values through the P5 program is effective in shaping student character. Additionally, this study highlights the importance of teacher support and a supportive school environment in ensuring the success of the program. Further research is needed to explore external factors, such as family environment and media, that may also influence students' character development.

Descriptive Statistics

Describes the basic characteristics of the data collected related to the Pearson correlation between the variables of effectiveness of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) and the improvement of student character.

1. The average Pearson correlation value is 0.828083, indicating a generally strong relationship between the project effectiveness variables of Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) and improving student character.
2. The standard deviation of 0.048318 shows that the variation in Pearson correlation values between items is not too large, indicating consistency in the strength of the relationship.
3. Pearson correlation values ranged from 0.740 (minimum) to 0.892 (maximum), all indicating a strong and significant relationship.

Descriptive statistics show that there is a strong and significant relationship between the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) and the improvement of student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta. All Pearson correlation values are significant at the 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$).

Project Impact on Student Character Improvement

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) has a very positive and significant impact on improving student character at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta.

Positive and Significant Impact

1. **Strong and Significant Relationship:** The results of the Pearson correlation analysis show that the effectiveness of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) has a very strong and significant relationship with the improvement of student character. All Pearson correlation values are significant at the 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$).
2. **Student Character Improvement:** The high correlation value indicates that the more effective the implementation of the Pancasila learner profile strengthening project (P5), the higher the improvement of student character. This indicates that the components in the project of

strengthening the profile of Pancasila students (P5) are successfully implemented well and have a positive impact on student character.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study concludes that the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project (P5) at SMAK 7 PENABUR Jakarta significantly contributes to improving students' character, particularly in the dimensions of faith and piety toward God, collaboration, independence, global diversity, critical thinking, and creativity. The findings show that the P5 program, which involves active student participation in activities based on Pancasila values, is effective in shaping students' character comprehensively. Moreover, teacher support and a supportive school environment play a crucial role in the success of this program.

The implications of this research are highly relevant to the development of character education in schools, especially in the context of the implementation of the Merdeka Belajar Curriculum. Schools can utilize these findings to evaluate the P5 program, focusing on enhancing student participation and involving teachers more actively in Pancasila values-based learning activities. Additionally, these results provide a foundation for developing more comprehensive educational policies to support the formation of student character based on Pancasila values, not only at SMAK 7 PENABUR but also in other schools.

This study has several limitations that should be noted. First, the research was conducted in only one school, so the results may not be entirely generalizable to schools with different characteristics. Second, the study employed only quantitative methods, leaving out the qualitative perspective that could provide deeper insights into the experiences of students and teachers during the P5 implementation. Furthermore, external factors, such as family environment or social media exposure, were not explored in depth, even though these factors may have a significant impact on the students' character development.

Based on the findings and limitations, several recommendations can be made. First, further research should be conducted in other schools with different characteristics to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of the P5 program. Second, using a mixed-method approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods, is recommended to gain deeper insights into the impact of P5 on students' character development. Future research could also broaden the scope by considering the influence of external factors, such as family involvement and media, which may affect the effectiveness of the P5 program in shaping students' character.

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APPENDIX**QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS**

NAME :

CLASS :

Instructions:

This questionnaire aims to measure your attitude and perception towards Pancasila values and the character changes you experienced during the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5). Please read each statement carefully and choose the answer that best reflects your opinion. Your responses will be kept confidential and used solely for this research purpose.

Likert Scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree | 2 = Disagree | 3 = Neutral | 4 = Agree | 5 = Strongly Agree

Section A: Attitude Toward Pancasila Values

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	I feel more faithful and devoted to God Almighty after participating in P5.					
2	I have greater appreciation and respect for cultural diversity after participating in P5.					
3	I collaborate more often with my peers in school activities after participating in P5.					
4	I feel more independent in completing school tasks after participating in P5.					
5	I am better at critical thinking and problem-solving after participating in P5.					
6	I feel more creative in finding solutions to various challenges after participating in P5.					

Section B: Perception of P5 Implementation

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
7	Group discussions during P5 helped me understand the values of Pancasila.					
8	Collaborative projects during P5 made me appreciate the importance of teamwork.					
9	Extracurricular activities held during P5 were highly beneficial for my character development.					
10	The community service program in P5 made me more aware of my surroundings.					
11	Teachers set good examples of how to apply Pancasila values in daily life.					
12	I feel that the evaluations and feedback given during P5 helped me improve myself.					

Source : Author's Data Processing